

Studies on the Amphoteric Nature of Hydrrous Molybdic Oxide

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From a study of equilibria of hydrrous molybdic oxide in dilute nitric acid, the isoelectric point has been located at pH 1.7 and the values of acid and base dissociation constants have been found to be 5.77×10^{-2} and 7.66×10^{-13} respectively.

An outstanding characteristic of the molybdates is their strong tendency to form condensed complex ions in acid solutions. In strongly acid solutions, hydrrous molybdic oxide is precipitated which in turn dissolves, when the solutions are made still more acidic, to form molybdenyl compounds. Although much work has been published on the aggregation of molybdate ion in solution, there are meagre references about the precipitation and amphoteric nature of the hydrrous molybdic oxide.

Little is known about the exact position of the isoelectric point of the molybdic acid. From diffusion experiments, Jander *et al.*¹ located this point at pH 0.9. Their measurements were, however, made in presence of considerable amounts of neutral salts which, as was shown by Carpeni², led to an increase in the magnitude of the dissociation constants of the acid and accordingly to a lowering of pH corresponding to its isoelectric point. Emeleus and Anderson³ opine that the diffusion method cannot furnish very precise data and the results must be considered in conjugation with other evidences.

Michaleis⁴ has suggested that the isoelectric point can be determined by adding portions of the ampholyte (if it is readily soluble) to a series of dilute buffer solutions. The buffer with pH equal to the isoelectric point would suffer no change. This method was contradicted by later workers. Fricke and Lonhard⁵ opined that if buffer solutions were used, the isoelectric point would be far different owing to ion adsorption. They showed that isoelectric point of bayerite $[Al(OH)_3]$ corresponded to a value 6.78 in a borate buffer, 5.59 in an acetate buffer, and 4.05 in a phosphate buffer.

Issa and Khalifa⁶ considered the method of determining the isoelectric point from solubility data as more reliable and reasonable and adopted this method for molybdic oxide obtained by the ignition of ammonium molybdate. But Schufenborgh⁷ pointed out that the isoelectric point of ampholytes, e.g., $Al(OH)_3$ or $Fe(OH)_3$, depended on the pretreatment of

1. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 194, 383.

2. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1947, 14, 496.

3. "Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry", 1952, p. 210.

4. "H⁺-Ion Concentration", Palazauweig, Williams and Wilkins Co., 1926, p. 5.

5. *Naturwiss.*, 1950, 37, 428.

6. *This Journal*, 1954, 31, 91.

7. *Trans. Intern. Cong. Soil Sci.*, 4th Congress, Amsterdam, 1950, p. 63.

the sample and showed that ignited or boiled samples had the isoelectric points at lower pH.

In view of the above contradictions, it was deemed advisable to redetermine the isoelectric point of hydrous molybdic oxide and also its dissociation constants from solubility measurements. The present communication deals with the values for the above physico-chemical constants.

EXPERIMENTAL

A sample of the suspension of the hydrous molybdic oxide was prepared and the constituents estimated as described in an earlier communication⁸. A standard solution of dilute HNO₃ was prepared from C. P. acid and its strength checked by a volumetric titration with a standardised alkali solution.

Each of the suspensions of molybdic oxide (10 ml) was introduced into various 100 ml flasks. Increasing quantities of dilute nitric acid were added to the suspensions and the total volume was made to the mark in every case. These solutions were shaken thoroughly and left overnight at the room temperature for attainment of saturation and equilibrium. The pH values of the solutions after saturation were measured with a Beckman pH meter using glass and calomel (saturated) electrodes and those of various amounts of nitric acid adjusted to the same strength, as in the dissolution experiments, were also measured and designated as pH values before saturation. A definite volume of the solution after saturation was then centrifuged and the molybdenum content determined both gravimetrically as lead molybdate and volumetrically by a method recommended by Korlov⁹. The results obtained by both the methods agreed within 0.5% (Table I).

TABLE I

Determination of isoelectric point and dissociation constants of molybdic acid.

Temperature = 26°.

Initial moles of HNO ₃ /10 ml.	pH of the solution.		S (g. moles of MoO ₃ /100 ml).	K _a .	K _b .
	Before saturation.	After saturation.			
2.432 × 10 ⁻²	1.05	0.95	1.949 × 10 ⁻²	1.691 × 10 ⁻¹	2.391 × 10 ⁻¹³
1.414 × 10 ⁻²	1.40	1.25	1.469 × 10 ⁻²	1.183 × 10 ⁻¹	3.741 × 10 ⁻¹³
1.009 × 10 ⁻²	1.50	1.40	1.259 × 10 ⁻²	7.233 × 10 ⁻²	4.560 × 10 ⁻¹³
8.076 × 10 ⁻³	1.55	1.45	1.140 × 10 ⁻²	5.982 × 10 ⁻²	4.753 × 10 ⁻¹³
4.038 × 10 ⁻³	1.80	1.65	9.895 × 10 ⁻³	3.462 × 10 ⁻²	6.902 × 10 ⁻¹³
3.028 × 10 ⁻³	1.95	1.80	8.395 × 10 ⁻³	2.263 × 10 ⁻²	9.016 × 10 ⁻¹³
2.019 × 10 ⁻³	2.10	1.95	8.406 × 10 ⁻³	1.628 × 10 ⁻²	1.201 × 10 ⁻¹³
1.414 × 10 ⁻³	2.30	2.10	8.574 × 10 ⁻³	1.161 × 10 ⁻²	1.321 × 10 ⁻¹³
1.036 × 10 ⁻³	3.30	3.00	8.672 × 10 ⁻³	1.520 × 10 ⁻²	1.250 × 10 ⁻¹³

8. *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1960, 29, IIIA, 230.

9. *J. Gen. Chem. USSR.*, 1932, 2, 661.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1, which is obtained by plotting the solubility of molybdic acid in dilute HNO_3 solutions against $p\text{H}$ values after saturation, shows that the solubility passes through a minimum at $p\text{H}$ 1.7 corresponding to the isoelectric point of the sample¹⁰.

FIG. 1

By comparing the $p\text{H}$ values after and before saturation (Table I), the solubility of the oxide appears to lower down the $p\text{H}$ of the solutions. It is fairly well established that an ampholyte possesses equal opportunities to dissociate within the isoelectric zone, either as an acid or a base. Outside that zone, either of the two processes may prevail, the acid dissociation above the isoelectric point and the basic dissociation below it. Consequently any ampholyte acts as a base towards buffer of $p\text{H}$ values lower than its isoelectric point, tending to raise the $p\text{H}$, and as an acid to buffers of higher $p\text{H}$ values, tending to lower the same.

Issa and Awad¹¹ are of the opinion that this levelling down or up of the $p\text{H}$ values of the solutions by the solubility of the ampholyte depends on the extent of its dissociation constants from a consideration of the values of K_a and K_b of molybdic acid which amount to $\sim 10^{-2}$ and 10^{-13} respectively¹². It can be visualised that molybdic acid dissociates more pronouncedly as an acid above its isoelectric point than as a base below that point. Our results show that the solubility of molybdic acid levels down the $p\text{H}$ of the solution above the isoelectric point as expected. But since it has a weak basic dissociation and low solubility, a lowering of $p\text{H}$ value below the isoelectric point as well is observed instead of a rise. A rise in $p\text{H}$ values is likely to be observed at still lower $p\text{H}$ of the solution where solubility might be higher and the basic dissociation predominant. In fact such values have been reported by Issa and Khalifa⁶ who have shown that the solubility of molybdic oxide levels down the $p\text{H}$ of solutions with values to 1.42, whereas it levels up at still lower $p\text{H}$ values of 0.6 and below.

10. Loeb, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1918, 1, 363.

11. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 948.

12. Novoselova, *J. Gen. Chem., USSR.*, 1931, 1, 688.

Dissociation Constants of Molybdic Acid

By using a relation given by Krebs and Speakman¹³, the above solubility data may be applied for determining the dissociation constants K_a and K_b of the molybdic acid species, stable in the vicinity of the isoelectric point. According to them, the acidic and basic dissociation constants may be evaluated from the relations:

$$(i) \quad \text{Log } S/S_0 - 1 = pH - pK_a$$

$$(ii) \quad \text{Log } S/S_0 - 1 = (pK_w - pK_b) - pH$$

where S represents the solubility at the given pH and S_0 , the solubility in strongly acid solutions. This latter value is obtained by plotting S against $(1/[H^+])$ and extrapolating to $(1/[H^+]) = 0$. The values of K_a and K_b , shown in Table I, were obtained by substituting in the above relations the $\log (S/S_0 - 1)$ values calculated at different pH values.

The results show that K_a values range from 1.16 to 7.23×10^{-2} and K_b values from 2.93 to 12.01×10^{-13} , which are in agreement with the values reported by Novoselova¹².

It may be mentioned here that the K_a and K_b values obtained from the above relations can be considered to represent the true dissociation constants only when the acid is monobasic and the base, monoacidic. If on the other hand, the acid is polybasic and the base polyacidic, they represent the mean of the different dissociation constants, unless the first dissociation constant is the predominating one, *i.e.*, if the other constants are comparatively small.

The authors are grateful to Prof. A. K. Bhattacharya, Head of the Department of Chemistry, for his keen interest in these investigations.

13. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 593.